

O.O. Tsypliak, V.O. Artemchuk

LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS IMPACT ONTO GATED COMMUNITIES SOCIAL MEDIA RESILIENCE

Urbanism as sociology segment that studies towns and cites more than two decades ago started the discussion about “gated communities”. [1] Meaning social and organizational communities behind some large residence places separated from outer town by a gate in some form. [2]

In modern Ukraine clear example of gated communities can be smaller like:

- Modern housing estates/complexes
- Old courtyard framed by soviet period multi-apartment building

Or larger like villages or small towns logistically separated from neighborhoods. The idea remains the same large group of people who are majorly hardly acquainted with each other have to live together, obviously having common problems, interests and shared resources like yards or parking spots to use.

Sociology studies phenomenon of gated communities as a one of the most common modern social self-organization that got significant impact onto the way modern cities grow and develop. (see picture 1) On the other hand the resilience of such community is a key to higher live quality of all residents.

Picture 1. Gated Communities Impact

Modern generative artificial intelligence (AI) after recent economical grown in 2021 impacted many areas of modern economy [3]. During following years AI investments into majority of areas decreased dramatically, but one of exceptional areas is social medias that keep engaging more and AI investments every years showing significant grows larger than other areas.

There are many studies showing demonstrating tools for text summarization and automated analysis [4]. Only the matter of time when new tools in social medias will appear that will dramatically impact the way people communicate each other in gated communities.

The way modern social networks are designed is far beyond just digitalizing physical group meeting, that were out to resolve common problems of some gated communities. [5] Social medias like Facebook and Twitter impacted the way people communicate overall.

Nowadays “Private Groups” of a yard or housing complex in Viber or Telegram is not only a platform for discussion, its also a storage of a lot of data that single participant willingly shares about oneself via messages available to big group of people.

All these data are stored social media hosting side, and assured to be secure. But in fact these data may got leak even though single stollen personal account of a group participant or using bots [6]. And considering modern generative AI as a fruit of large language models development[7] all this data can be used in multiple possible harmful ways for social medias users from certain gated communities, for example to design unwanted advertisements or share personal profile with a third parties.

In conclusion, gated community is a form of residence self-organization that started as digitalized platforms to discuss problems and be used for socialization. Consequence of such digitalization of last decades resulted into low unsecured private groups contains a lot of sensitive personal information that can be used to harm social media users from gated communities.

To remain resistant and transparent such groups should be considered as source of personal information leak that considering modern generative AI progress can be used against social media users as cheap as never before. How this process can be prevented using cybersecurity or social engineering is a subject of further studies.

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